

Synthesis science – The PARSEC approach

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PARSEC project

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We all love nature!

But our footprint keep impacting it...

HUMAN DEVELOPMENT AND EARTH'S SYSTEMS

The Great Acceleration, and the rapid and immense social, economic and ecological changes it has spurred, show us that we are in a period of great upheaval. Some of these changes have been positive, some negative, and all of them are interconnected. What is increasingly clear is that human development and wellbeing are reliant on healthy natural systems, and we cannot continue to enjoy the former without the latter.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC TRENDS

EARTH SYSTEM TRENDS

Figure 3: The Great Acceleration

The increasing rates of change in human activity since the beginning of the Industrial Revolution. The 1950s marks an explosion in growth. After this time, human activities (left panels) begin to interfere significantly with Earth's life support system (right panels) (these graphs are from Steffen et al., 2015³⁶ and all the references to the datasets behind them are in the original paper).

... in a very very short time...

... posing various threats to nature

Figure 11: Primary threats to LPI populations
Information on threats has been identified for 3,430 populations in the LPI assigned to seven categories. Other populations are either not threatened or lack threat information (WWF, ZSL, 2014).

Examples of in the marine environment

Demersal Destructive Fishing

Nutrient Input

Climate Change (SST)

Ocean Acidification

Commercial Activity (Shipping)

Invasive Species

Those impacts are cumulative

(Halpern, 2008)

Example of threat – Fishing (trawling)

(after Christen, 1999)

(after Messieh et al., 1991)

Before trawling

Copyright - A. Freiwald

After trawling

Copyright - The Mountains-in-the-Sea Research Team, IPE, IUCN, IAO, and NOAA

Outcome: an alarming global decline of wildlife

Figure 20: The Global Living Planet Index: 1970 to 2014
Average abundance of 16,704 populations representing 4,005 species monitored across the globe declined by 60%. The white line shows the index values and the shaded areas represent the statistical certainty surrounding the trend (range: -50% to -67%)¹.

Key

- Global Living Planet Index
- Confidence limits

WILDLIFE POPULATION DECLINE BETWEEN 1970 AND 2010

76%
Freshwater species

39%
Terrestrial species

39%
Marine species

SOURCE: World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF)

CORNYNEZ TORRE

Protected areas

-

Not a silver bullet, but a cornerstone
of conservation strategies

WWII effect on fisheries

"The Great Fishing Experiment"

Figure 1. Total European fish landings. Eastern North Atlantic, 1935-1949 (t)

Source: ICES database

Holm (2012)

Figure 2. Time trends of international landings (°, in '000 t) and combined c.p.u.e. index (•)

Source: A.D. Rijnsdorp, R.S. Millner, *Trends in Population Dynamics and Exploitation of North Sea Plaice (*Pleuronectes platessa* L.) since the Late 1800s*, ICES Journal of Marine Science, 53, 1996, pp. 1170-1184

Or in short : the less you fish, the more fish you will find in the water!

2010: UN Aichi Biodiversity Convention

- 20 different targets

Aichi Targets					
15	Enhance resilience				
16	Implement Nagoya Prot.				
17	Revise NBSAPs				
18	Respect and conserve TK				
19	Improve knowledge				
20	Mobilize resources				
14	Restore ecosystems				

Aiming for “at least 17 per cent of terrestrial and inland water areas and 10 per cent of coastal and marine areas...” before 2020

Protected areas: an ambiguous term

In practice, “protected areas” is just a name; the level of protection and other characteristics make all the difference

Protected areas are supposed to be a tool for nature conservation (i.e. IUCN definition). But for many, it is also a tool for people (sometimes as primary goal) - e.g. tourism, economic boost

Protected Areas Classification (by goal)

Strict protection

Category I – Protected area managed mainly for science or wilderness protection (Strict Nature Reserve/Wilderness Area);

Category II – Protected area managed mainly for ecosystem protection and recreation (National Park);

Category III – Protected area managed mainly for conservation of specific natural features (Natural Monument);

Category IV – Protected area managed mainly for conservation through management intervention (Habitat/Species Management Area);

Category V – Protected area managed mainly for landscape/seascape conservation and recreation (Protected Landscape/Seascape);

Category VI – Protected area managed mainly for the sustainable use of natural ecosystems (Managed Resource Protected Area).

(IUCN, 1994)

MPA zoning: Single vs multiple zoning/protection

Example: Great Barrier Reef, Australia

CORAL

SEA

DRAFT ACTIVITIES GUIDE (see Draft Zoning Plan for details)

	General Use Zone	Habitat Protection Zone	Conservation Park Zone	Buffer Zone	Scientific Research Zone	Marine National Park Zone	Preservation Zone
Aquaculture	Permit	Permit ¹	No	No	No	No	No
Bait netting	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No
Boating, diving, photography	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes ²	Yes	No
Collecting	Permit	Permit	No	No	No	No	No
Commercial netting	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No
Crabbing	Yes	Yes	Limited ³	No	No	No	No
Harvest fisheries (eg. bêche-de-mer, tropical rock lobster, aquanum fish)	Permit ⁴	Permit ⁴	No	No	No	No	No
Limited collecting (includes bait and oyster gathering)	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No
Limited impact research	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes ⁵	Yes	Yes ⁵	Permit
Limited spearfishing (snorkel only)	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No
Line fishing ⁶	Yes	Yes	Limited ⁷	No	No	No	No
Research	Permit	Permit	Permit	Permit	Permit	Permit	Permit
Shipping (other than shipping area)	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
Tourism program	Permit	Permit	Permit	Permit	Permit	Permit	No
Traditional use of marine resources ⁸							No
Trawling	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
Trolling (for pelagic species)	Yes	Yes	Yes ⁷	Yes	No	No	No

Islands: All Commonwealth owned islands in the Great Barrier Reef Marine Park are zoned "Commonwealth Islands Zone". See the Draft Zoning Plan for details.

1. Aquaculture operations which do not include the addition of feed.
2. Scientific Research Zones at One Tree Island and the Australian Institute of Marine Science have public access restrictions. See the Draft Zoning Plan for details.
3. No more than 4 catch devices per person.
4. Accredited harvest fisheries may be conducted 'as of right' in the Zone.
5. Permit required if research is extractive.
6. Maximum of 3 lines/rods per person with a combined total of 6 hooks/lures.
7. Limited to 1 line/rod per person and 1 hook/lure per line.
8. Traditional use does not include activities that are otherwise as of right within each Zone (eg. limited collecting, line fishing, crabbing, etc.). A permit is required for traditional use if the activity is not as of right in the Zone, or involves hunting, unless it is conducted under a Traditional Use of Marine Resources Agreement approved by the GBRMPA.

For clarification of any points or further information, contact the Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Authority.

Emergencies: Access to all zones is allowed in emergencies.

Where are we globally ?(end 2022)

2020

17% =>

2030

< 30%

10% =>

<< 30%

Heterogeneous distribution of PAs

Between 2010 and 2019

From 14.1% to 15% for Terrestrial From 2.9% to 7.5% for Marine

Trends since 1990

Change in protected area and OECM coverage since 1990

We reach a plateau far from 30% coverage

More protected areas is good, right?

Well... it depends...

How much of this protection is real?

In other words: do MPAs work?

- Answer: it depends...
- *When designed properly* **MPAs work** (proven for >20 years)
- MPAs with **higher levels of protection provide significantly higher benefits** (e.g. species diversity, biomass, ecosystem health)

MPA biological effectiveness confirmed

Many evidence in the literature of ecological benefits of MPAs
= General agreement of their ecological effectiveness in the literature

But protection level is key

nature communications

Article

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-32035-3>

Small-scale fisheries catch more threatened elasmobranchs inside partially protected areas than in unprotected areas

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Check for updates

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Elasmobranchs are heavily impacted by fishing. Catch statistics are grossly underestimated due to missing data from various fishery sectors such as small-scale fisheries. Marine Protected Areas are proposed as a tool to protect elasmobranchs and counter their ongoing depletion. We assess elasmobranchs caught in 1,256 fishing operations with fixed nets carried out in partially protected areas within Marine Protected Areas and unprotected areas beyond Marine Protected Areas borders at 11 locations in 6 Mediterranean countries. Twenty-four elasmobranch species were recorded, more than one-third belonging to the IUCN threatened categories (Vulnerable, Endangered, or Critically Endangered). Catches per unit of effort of threatened and data deficient species were higher (with more immature individuals being caught) in partially protected areas than in unprotected areas. Our study suggests that despite partially protected areas having the potential to deliver ecological benefits for threatened elasmobranchs, poor small-scale fisheries management inside Marine Protected Areas could hinder them from achieving this important conservation objective.

But protection level is key

Conservation Biology

Contributed Paper

Evaluating the social and ecological effectiveness of partially protected marine areas

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Abstract: Marine protected areas (MPAs) are a primary tool for the stewardship, conservation, and restoration of marine ecosystems, yet 69% of global MPAs are only partially protected (i.e., are open to some form of fishing). Although fully protected areas have well-documented outcomes, including increased fish diversity and biomass, the effectiveness of partially protected areas is contested. Partially protected areas may provide benefits in some contexts and may be warranted for social reasons, yet social outcomes often depend on MPAs achieving their ecological goals to distinguish them from open areas and justify the cost of protection. We assessed the social perceptions and ecological effectiveness of 18 partially protected areas and 19 fully protected areas compared with 19 open areas along 7000 km of coast of southern Australia. We used mixed methods, gathering data via semistructured interviews, site surveys, and Reef Life (underwater visual census) surveys. We analyzed qualitative data in accordance with grounded theory and quantitative data with multivariate and univariate linear mixed-effects models. We found no social or ecological benefits for partially protected areas relative to open areas in our study. Partially protected areas had no more fish, invertebrates, or algae than open areas; were poorly understood by coastal users; were not more attractive than open areas; and were not perceived to have better marine life than open areas. These findings provide an important counterpoint to some large-scale meta-analyses that conclude partially protected areas can be ecologically effective but that draw this conclusion based on narrower measures. We argue that partially protected areas act as red herrings in marine conservation because they create an illusion of protection and consume scarce conservation resources yet provide little or no social or ecological gain over open areas. Fully protected areas, by contrast, have more fish species and biomass and are well understood, supported, and valued by the public. They are perceived to have better marine life and be improving over time in keeping with actual ecological results. Conservation outcomes can be improved by upgrading partially protected areas to higher levels of protection including conversion to fully protected areas.

“We found no social or ecological benefits for partially protected areas relative to open areas in our study”

or in other words:
partial protection does nothing to nature or people

Turnbull et al. (2021)

MPAs need to mitigate threats

“We found that 59% of MPAs are commercially trawled, and **average trawling intensity across MPAs is at least 1.4-fold higher as compared with nonprotected areas**”

RESEARCH

MARINE PROTECTED AREAS

Elevated trawling inside protected areas undermines conservation outcomes in a global fishing hot spot

Manuel Dureuil^{1,2*}, Kristina Boerder¹, Kirsti A. Burnett², Rainer Froese³, Boris Worm¹

Marine protected areas (MPAs) are increasingly used as a primary tool to conserve biodiversity. This is particularly relevant in heavily exploited fisheries hot spots such as Europe, where MPAs now cover 29% of territorial waters, with unknown effects on fishing pressure and conservation outcomes. We investigated industrial trawl fishing and sensitive indicator species in and around 727 MPAs designated by the European Union.

We found that 59% of MPAs are commercially trawled, and average trawling intensity across MPAs is at least 1.4-fold higher as compared with nonprotected areas. Abundance of sensitive species (sharks, rays, and skates) decreased by 69% in heavily trawled areas. The widespread industrial exploitation of MPAs undermines global biodiversity conservation targets, elevating recent concerns about growing human pressures on protected areas worldwide.

In light of mounting anthropogenic pressures, spatial protection of sensitive habitats and species has emerged as a leading strategy to halt ongoing biodiversity loss, both on land and in the sea (1). However, it has been shown recently that about one-third of terrestrial protected areas experience intense human pressure, potentially undermining global conservation targets and sustainable development goals (2). We asked to which extent this conflict may also occur in the ocean, using newly available satellite sensors that allow fine-scale, real-time quantification of industrial fishing effort from space (3).

are often regulated under the EU Common Fisheries Policy (table S2).

By far the most common industrial fishing method in Europe is trawling (3), which targets mainly bottom-associated fishes, often with a high rate of unwanted bycatch (fig. S1). This fishing technique has been identified as a threat to many endangered species in Europe, including most elasmobranchs (sharks, rays, and skates) (9), and has well-documented impacts on seafloor biodiversity (10), sensitive habitats, and indicator species (11). We directly quantified the extent of commercial trawling in the EU with respect

What makes MPAs effective?

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NATURE | LETTER

[日本語要約](#)

Global conservation outcomes depend on marine protected areas with five key features

Graham J. Edgar, Rick D. Stuart-Smith, Trevor J. Willis, Stuart Kininmonth, Susan C. Baker, Stuart Banks, Neville S. Barrett, Mikel A. Becerro, Anthony T. F. Bernard, Just Berkhout, Colin D. Buxton, Stuart J. Campbell, Antonia T. Cooper, Marlene Davey, Sophie C. Edgar, Günter Försterra, David E. Galván, Alejo J. Irigoyen, David J. Kushner, Rodrigo Moura, P. Ed Parnell, Nick T. Shears, German Soler, Elisabeth M. A. Strain & Russell J. Thomson

5 key features:

No-take
well Enforced
Old
Large
Isolated

MPA classification by protection levels (by expected outcome)

The MPA guide (2021)

MPA classification by protection levels (by expected outcome)

Grorud-Colvert *et al.* (2021) *Science*

Marine protected areas by protection levels

Regulation-Based Classification System Marine Protection

1% of ocean area is implemented and in RBCS levels 1-3

2.3% is implemented and in RBCS levels 4-7

3.6% of the area in designated zones has been assessed to date

Overview

The Regulation-Based Classification System (RBCS) classifies MPAs using a globally applicable, decision tree framework based on regulations using an increasing gradient of impacts of uses (1-8).

Click on an MPA zone in the map for more information. Use the filter charts below to display a subset of MPA zones.

Note: only areas that meet the IUCN definition of MPA are shown here.

379 zones are visible within the map.
 show 16069 unassessed MPA zones

RBCS Protection Level

RBCS 1: No-take / No-go	24 zones
RBCS 2: No-take / Regulated Access	81 zones
RBCS 3: No-take / Unregulated Access	19 zones
RBCS 4: Highly Regulated Extraction	104 zones
RBCS 5: Moderately Regulated Extraction	70 zones
RBCS 6: Weakly Regulated Extraction	68 zones
RBCS 7: Very Weakly Regulated Extraction	13 zones
RBCS 8: Unregulated Extraction	0 zones

Establishment Stage

Designated / Implemented	369 zones
Designated / unimplemented	9 zones
Proposed / committed	1 zones

Yet, still far from conservation targets

Global Conservation Progress

Why people are still reluctant to establish protected areas?

The link between PAs and socioeconomic outcomes is not clear!

Some success stories

Some terrible stories

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Emergent conservation conflicts in the Galapagos Islands: Human-giant tortoise interactions in the rural area of Santa Cruz Island

Francisco Benitez-Capistros^{1,2,3}*, Giorgia Camperio^{3,4,5}*, Jean Hugé^{2,3,6,7}‡, Farid Dahdouh-Guebas^{3,4}‡, Nico Koedam³‡

New challenge

CONSERVATION

Landscapes that work for biodiversity and people

C. Kremen* and A. M. Merenlender

Key question:

Are there any long-term socioeconomic
benefits of protected areas?

This question is not new

ANALYSIS

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0306-2>

nature
sustainability

Well-being outcomes of marine protected areas

Natalie C. Ban^{1*}, Georgina Grace Gurney², Nadine A. Marshall³, Charlotte K. Whitney¹,
Morena Mills⁴, Stefan Gelcich⁵, Nathan J. Bennett^{6,7,8}, Mairi C. Meehan⁹, Caroline Butler¹⁰,
Stephen Ban¹¹, Tanya C. Tran¹, Michael E. Cox¹² and Sara Jo Breslow¹³

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Assessing the Effect of Marine Reserves on Household Food Security in Kenyan Coral Reef Fishing Communities

Emily S. Darling^{1,2,*}

SCIENCE ADVANCES | RESEARCH ARTICLE

ECONOMICS

Evaluating the impacts of protected areas on human well-being across the developing world

R. Naidoo^{1,2*}, D. Gerkey³, D. Hole⁴, A. Pfaff⁵, A. M. Ellis⁶, C. D. Golden⁷, D. Herrera⁸, K. Johnson^{9†},
M. Mulligan¹⁰, T. H. Ricketts¹¹, B. Fisher¹¹

But results are still controversial
and limited in space and in time

Our ambition

Assessing, in a standardized and replicable way, the temporal dynamic (>20 years) of several dimensions of human poverty and well-being in towns and villages close to a protected area

Our core hypothesis

Towns and villages close to a protected area can better alleviate poverty and support well-being than their counterparts without any management action on ecosystems

Our local socioeconomic outcomes

- Poverty
- Asset Health
- Tourism frequentation
- Child Growth Failure
- Consumption Expenditure

Our data and tools

The **DHS Program**
Demographic and Health Surveys

Our objectives

1. Choose ~ 100 towns and villages close to a protected area and select their mirror sites far from any protected area
1. Build a deep learning algorithm to predict the level of the chosen socioeconomic outcome (e.g. poverty) from satellite images
1. Assess the dynamics of the socioeconomic outcome over time in our ~ 100 selected sites and their mirrors to test our core hypothesis

Objective 1: choose sites and their mirrors

- Propositions of protected areas by each country
- Good balance between sites close to terrestrial vs. marine protected areas
- Sites in both developed and developing countries
 - Sites in countries with local surveys
- Mirror sites selected with a matching algorithm

Objective 2: deep learning algorithm

RESEARCH

RESEARCH ARTICLES

ECONOMICS

Combining satellite imagery and machine learning to predict poverty

Neal Jean,^{1,2*} Marshall Burke,^{3,4,5*†} Michael Xie,¹ W. Matthew Davis,⁴
David B. Lobell,^{3,4} Stefano Ermon¹

Objective 2: deep learning algorithm

LSMS
Living Standards Measurement Study

The **DHS** Program
Demographic and Health Surveys

Objective 3: assess and test PA benefits if any?

Before PA

Future PA site Mirror Site

come

After PA

-> outcome

Compare trajectories

X

-

Y

= BENEFIT

The PARSEC approach

Supports/advise on open science initiatives

Provides a real interdisciplinary research context to explore challenges and solutions

The need for synthesis

“ We are drowning in information while starving for wisdom ...

”

Edward O. Wilson (1998)
Consilience: The Unity of Knowledge

The need for synthesis

“ We are drowning in information while starving for wisdom ...

The world henceforth will be run by synthesizers, people able to put together the right information at the right time, think critically about it, and make important choices wisely ”

Edward O. Wilson (1998)
Consilience: The Unity of Knowledge

Synthesis strand

Synthesis strand

Different Countries -> Different Issues and Different Data

Synthesis work in the covid era

Conclusions

- Assessing the causal link between Protected Areas and Socioeconomic Outcomes is essential but still unachieved
- This causal link should rely on before-and-after designs and space-as-time designs
- Coupling big data and artificial intelligence algorithms is revolutionizing the assessment of SDGs and the achievement of their targets